

PRELIMINARY OBSERVATIONS ON THE ARCHITECTURE OF TEXTILE COMPOSITES USING MICRO-XRAY-CT

Nayeem T. Chowdhury¹, Garth Pearce¹.

¹ School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, UNSW, NSW, Australia.
nayeem.chowdhury@unsw.edu.au, www.unsw.edu.au

Keywords: Plain weave, Representative Volume Elements, micro-XRay-CT, Textile architecture, Meso-mechanical

ABSTRACT

Understanding failure within composite materials has been an ongoing area of research over the last several decades. A lot of newly emerging failure theories are starting to acknowledge this non-homogeneity using Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) where the properties of the fibre and matrix constituents are retained throughout the modelling process. To create meaningful RVEs at the meso-mechanical level, suitable methods need to be established that can capture the key geometric features within the material. Micro-Xray CT has been used in the past to visualise the textile architecture without destroying the material in the scanning process. However, there have been a lot of advancements in the technology since its first use within composites where contrast enhancement agents were used. This paper looks at identifying the textile architecture of composites at the meso-level without the use of contrast enhancement agents. Obtaining successful results without the use of any modifications to the material system itself has been an area of ongoing research for the past several years, where some of the most promising preliminary results achieved to date are presented in this paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are gaining huge interest within the aerospace industry. They are appealing due to their high strength to weight ratios and their ability to easily conform to manufacture various geometries. Unlike unidirectional tapes; which are unable to remain intact when draped over moulds, textile composites (fabrics and braids) are extremely prevalent in the design and fabrication of composite structures. Practical advantages over unidirectional tapes include their; handleability, drapability, reparability, bondability and damage tolerance. A big gap in textile composites is the common assumption that the material is homogenous or arranged in a perfect pattern. Realistically this is not the case and research is starting to look at how these details can be included within an analysis procedure [1, 2].

The consideration of fibre architecture on micromechanical failure events is directly applicable to a structural investigation as most composites used within the aerospace industry are in the form of textiles or hybrid laminated. Fig. 1, shows an example a micro and meso level fibre architecture. Using the digitised architecture, further insight about material properties and their interaction with damage progression can be gained. This will allow users to determine how important capturing a realistic fabric structure is to obtain an accurate failure prediction.

Figure 1: (a) Micro-level architecture for unitape, (b) meso-level fabric cross-section [3].

With advances in today's computing power and computational packages available to users, researchers have started to look at composites at the constituent level where micro/meso-mechanical approaches are taken [4, 5]. One of the first steps to perform such an investigation is to establish a Representative Volume Element (RVE) for the material. RVEs play a crucial part in a finite element investigation, as they are the building block upon which all loads/ boundary conditions are applied to extract micro- mechanical failure strains. This modelling approach has been presented extensively in literature [4, 6-8], However, RVEs do not capture the complex in-situ geometry of textiles. Failure, driven by local phenomena, are likely influenced strongly by the real geometry. Thus, performing pure micro-mechanical level analysis is likely to be anti-conservative. Instead an understanding of the meso-level fabric architectures are required.

Carbon fibre and epoxy resins systems are the two types of materials commonly used for composites in aerospace applications. The two constituents have distinctly different properties which is often responsible for the complicated material behaviour of the lamina. However, these two materials often share similar densities. From a visualisation perspective where micro-CT is used to examine the internal geometry of the textile architecture, this becomes a very difficult problem. Micro computed tomography allows you to inspect inside a material without having to destroy the specimen. It operates very much like medical CT systems, where slice by slice information is extracted in a patient's body without having to perform any cuts or incisions. The process of acquiring the images requires X-rays to be generated and then transmitted through the sample. During this process, the sample is rotated and a series of projections are acquired. These acquired images are then reconstructed to form virtual slices. The most difficult stage of the process for composites is the reconstruction of the virtual slices. Different density materials cause different amounts of X-ray to be absorbed and then transmitted onto the detector, since epoxy and carbon fibres have very similar densities; this visualisation technique suffers from achieving contrast between the two materials. On a good quality scan; visually, the human eye can distinguish key patterns. However, given that there are thousands of virtual slices and a very complicated textile architecture to examine, a computer algorithm is a necessity when reconstructing all the images to form a Volume Element of the material. It is in this stage that segmenting fibre bundles/yarns from adjacent ones and the resin becomes a problem for computer algorithms to handle.

In this paper, an overview on some common practices presented in literature to overcome this segmentation problem is presented and recent outcomes through improved accuracy in CT technology on the imaging of carbon fibre specimens without contrast enhancement agents is discussed. Currently the methodology to obtain scans of virgin specimens is hindering the large potential to use this technology within the industry. Once this hurdle is overcome the direction in which failure models and analytical techniques are used will see a large area of new research methods being developed. The methodology adopted to perform these preliminary tests approached the problem with the intention of achieve as good of a scan of the specimen from the CT machine, rather than rely on advanced algorithms to simplify and solve yarn boundaries and trajectories.

2 USE OF CONTRAST ENHANCEMENT

Contrast enhancements have been used for some time to examine the textile architecture of composites. The enhancement agents are chosen to have a distinctly different density compared to the two constituents so that a clear marker is able to be seen. What this means is that the composite specimens have to be modified during their manufacturing stage. Additives are often used within the resin so that phase differences can be seen. Other techniques include the coating of yarns using: Silicon Carbide (SiC), gold sputter, coating in gold, iodine and resin particles [9, 10]. These additives coat the often allow a bright contrast difference to be observed at the yarn boundaries. However, coating still did not completely solve the problem of identifying the textile architecture. It was found to in some cases that the type of coating used affected what could be seen in the internal tow interfaces [10, 11], whilst coating using aqueous solutions such as iodine were found to coat the interfaces properly yet neighbouring yarns were still hard to disseminate [11]. From these it can be overall stated that although the technique of using contrast enhancements did improve the segmentation process, key regions of

interest within the textile architecture remained difficult to see.

In addition to this, the biggest limitation of the technique is the fact that the material system itself is being altered. Thus, from a characterising point of view it is questionable as to whether a modified sample of this specimen will have the same properties as the virgin sample. When the overall objective of examining the fibre architecture in textiles is looked purely from a visualisation perspective in order to create Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) this procedure may suffice. However, when the intent to examine the fibre architecture is to observe the evolution of damage propagation and the effect the textile architecture has on this, then adding additive to the specimen becomes highly undesirable.

3 NO CONTRAST ENHANCEMENTS

The idea of using no contrast enhancement agents within the composite material appeal to users for a few main reasons; the ability to take a specimen from the manufacturing line and examine it for visual defects, and the possibility to perform in-situ testing to observe progressive damage without suffering from possible failure events arising due to the additives [12]. The method has been trialled in the past and its difficulty in processing the raw images has lead researchers to seek better contrast measures. Some common means to obtain a successful reconstructed image of the specimen involves the use of algorithms which look at statistically separating and approximating the boundaries between key features [13, 14]. literature has also shown methods which include the approximation of yarn shapes and orientations based on periodic cubic interpolation functions [13, 14], where manual selection of pixel coordinates are performed. The method can predict yarn paths and interactions with adjacent yarns and is a reasonable approximation to account for the complicated architecture of the composite. However, retaining information from the virtual slices without approximations allows for more than just the yarn trajectory to be observed. It can also allow the change in the yarn cross-section to be seen as it interacts with adjacent plies.

In this paper we look at a preliminary investigation on optimising the parameters for use on a micro-Xray-CT fixture such that a high resolution image is able to be achieved and important information can be extracted. Several scans using different parameters and specimen sizes were trialled. The latest set of parameters used on our in-house CT fixture used: 60kV with a 3.5 second exposure time and 3600 projections with a acquisition duration of 12 hours. A 2mm aluminium filter was used and a 3.41 μm voxel size was used. Fig. 2 shows an example of the achieved resolution and the detail in textile architecture.

Figure 2: Example of a raw slice taken using $\mu\text{X-CT}$ without the use of contrast enhancement for a T800S/3900-2 [0/90]₁₂ prepreg.

Visually it can be seen that there are key textural differences between the weft and warp yarns going into the page and coming out. Different algorithms can extract key features based on texture, pixel density and differences in colour gradients. Through manipulation of noise to signal and enhancing colour gradients at the outer faces of the yarns, a methodology was developed that could accurately identify the three phases of the material system: the matrix, weft and warp yarns. Texture

was identified as a preliminary means of segmenting the geometry, although it was found that the results were generally successful, issue at the regions where one yarn crosses the other showed concern, as the yarns don't necessarily always line up parallel to the plane of the slices. Thus, small regions of the material architecture look the same despite having crucial differences. A method in which the segmentation was found to have success especially in the overlapping regions was through increasing the noise in the images whilst retaining the signal strength. An example of this is shown in Fig. 3 (a). Fig. 3 (b) shows the segmented weft yarns picked up by the software. Note that there are four samples in the scan as they were stacked to form a square cross section to overcome beam hardening in our central region of interest.

(a) (b)
Figure 3: Processing of the virtual slices; (a) increased noise to enhance boundaries (tomogram), (b) Segmented and label tagged images.

The same procedure was followed for the perpendicular plane when slices were observed. Interestingly the intensity was different in the material plane which is an area of added interest to be investigated in a future study. The same methodology used for Fig. 3 was adopted for the warp yarns however different magnitudes were required. Note that after the label cluster identified different regions within the model. Small clusters were removed to simplify the RVE by establishing a threshold in which the volumes were considered not a primary concern for this preliminary investigation (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Warp yarns segmented and labelled.

Through a series of parameter adjustments looking at the Euclidean Distance Map (EDT) in non-tagged regions, we could remove small voids and artefacts within the material to simplify the RVE being extracted. The Euclidean distance map for the labelled regions shown in Fig. 3 (b) is shown in Fig. 5 (a). This can be seen in a different means where a 3D covering sphere map was applied on the EDT, this is shown in Fig. 5 (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: segmentation of the weft tows, (a) using a EDT of the labelled area, (b) 3D covering sphere map shown in Figure 5 (a)

The process allowed the edges of the yarns to be clearly identified and their interactions and paths can be further analysed by modelling their trajectories. When the segmented images from the weft and warp yarns are combined, we obtain Fig. 6, where the remaining area is assumed to be purely resin.

Figure 6: Segmented warp and weft yarns combined to form a meso-level architecture for composite material.

Note that the sides of the scanned specimen have questionable boundaries which were expected due to the asymmetry of the specimen. The main point of interest in our specimens is the central region which is why several specimens were stacked together to improve against beam hardening.

4 REPRESENTATIVE VOLUME ELEMENT

With the virtual slices segmented with two identifiable fibre domains (i.e. the weft and warp yarns) the matrix domain was assumed to be taken as the subtraction of the two fibre domains from a unit cell. Fig. 7 shows the reconstructed material. The image shown in Fig. 7 shows a level of detail that to the authors knowledge has not been seen for any reconstructed images of the textile architecture of a carbon fibre-epoxy composite without the use of enhancement agents. The images achieved are also arguably better than that observed for scans of textile composites which do use contrast enhancement agents. This paper is concluded with these results, however for the next stage the images will be examined by sectioning out key regions of the scan and performing a statistical analysis to account for stochastic differences within the fabric. Key patterns will be observed and the importance of retaining some of these geometric patterns within the RVE will be investigated using FEA.

Figure 7: Reconstructed composite specimen fibre bundles only.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The basis of this paper was to give an overview of the preliminary results achieved using no contrast enhancement agents to scan carbon fibre composites which have historically been very difficult to scan and obtain virtual slices with enough contrast and detail so that three-dimensional Representative Volume Elements can be created. The results achieved in this paper demonstrated that with a detailed investigation on the parameters of the CT scanning parameters and the type of CT machine used (in this case the CT fixture was designed in house with parts sourced from different suppliers). These results give a promising look into the future characterization of composites where geometry based failure events can be looked at in-situ to enable progressive failure mechanisms to be looked into.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Wang, X. Wang, J. Zhang, W. Liang, and L. Zhou, "Automatic generation of random distribution of fibers in long-fiber-reinforced composites and mesomechanical simulation," *Materials & Design*, vol. 32, pp. 885-891, 2011.
- [2] Y. Y. Lei Yang, Jian Ma, Bo Liu, "Effects of inter-fiber spacing and thermal residual stress on transverse failure of fiber-reinforced polymer-matrix composites," *Computational Materials Science*, vol. 68, pp. 255-262, 2013.
- [3] L. P. Djukic, G. M. Pearce, I. Herszberg, M. K. Bannister, and D. H. Mollenhauer, "Contrast Enhancement of MicroCT Scans to Aid 3D Modelling of Carbon Fibre Fabric Composites," *Applied Composite Materials*, vol. 20, pp. 1215-1230, 2013// 2013.
- [4] R. Pipes and J. Gosse, "An onset theory for irreversible deformation in composite materials," in *ICCM-17, the 17th international conference on composite materials, Edinburgh, UK*, 2009, p. 31.
- [5] N. T. Chowdhury, "A novel failure criterion for matrix dominant failure within fibre reinforced polymer composites," Doctor of Philosophy, Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Monash University. Faculty of Engineering. Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, 2016.
- [6] N. T. Chowdhury, W. K. Chiu, J. Wang, and W. Yan, "Predicting matrix failure in composite structures using a hybrid failure criterion," *Composite Structures*, vol. 137, pp. 148-158, 2016.
- [7] N. T. Chowdhury, J. Wang, W. K. Chiu, and W. Yan, "Matrix failure in composite laminates under compressive loading," *Composites: Part A*, vol. 84, pp. 103-113, 2016.
- [8] N. T. Chowdhury, J. Wang, W. K. Chiu, and W. Yan, "Matrix failure in composite laminates under tensile loading," *Composite Structures*, vol. 135, pp. 61-73, 1// 2016.
- [9] H. Bale, M. Blacklock, M. R. Begley, D. B. Marshall, B. N. Cox, and R. O. Ritchie, "Characterizing Three-Dimensional Textile Ceramic Composites Using Synchrotron X-Ray Micro-Computed-Tomography," *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, vol. 95, pp. 392-402, 2012.
- [10] L. P. Djukic, I. Herszberg, W. R. Walsh, G. A. Schoeppner, B. Gangadhara Prusty, and D. W. Kelly, "Contrast enhancement in visualisation of woven composite tow architecture using a MicroCT Scanner. Part 1: Fabric coating and resin additives," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 40, pp. 553-565, 5// 2009.
- [11] L. P. Djukic, I. Herszberg, W. R. Walsh, G. A. Schoeppner, and B. Gangadhara Prusty, "Contrast enhancement in visualisation of woven composite architecture using a MicroCT Scanner. Part 2: Tow and preform coatings," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 40, pp. 1870-1879, 12// 2009.
- [12] H. Wang and Z.-w. Wang, "Statistical Analysis of Yarn Feature Parameters in C/Epoxy Plain-Weave Composite Using Micro CT with High-Resolution Lens-Coupled Detector," *Applied Composite Materials*, vol. 23, pp. 601-622, 2016.
- [13] L. Hua, S. Martin, C. Jonathan, C. L. Andrew, J. C. Mike, and I. A. Jones, "Finite element modelling of fabric compression," *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 16, p. 035010, 2008.
- [14] L. Hua, J. C. Mike, C. L. Andrew, and S. Martin, "Finite element modelling of fabric shear," *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 17, p. 015008, 2009.